

Performance Study of Deep Learning Activation Function

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Abstract— In recent years, the deep learning computing paradigm has been regarded as the Gold Standard in the machine learning community. In addition, deep learning is gradually becoming the most widely used computational approach in machine learning, achieving amazing results on some complex cognitive tasks, even beating human performance. Deep learning has been widely used to handle various applications, such as cybersecurity, bioinformatics, robotics and control, medical information processing, etc. Therefore, in this paper, the author analyzes various activation function that are often applied to deep learning, including ReLU, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu. This paper will end with a collection of data from various deep learning activation function (ReLU, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu) as well as summaries and conclusions.

Keywords— Deep Learning, Machine Learning, Application

I. INTRODUCTION

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of neural network commonly used in image data. CNN can be used to detect and recognize objects in an image. CNN have fewer connections and parameters, so they are easier to train.

CNN was first developed under the name NeoCognitron by Kunihiko Fukushima, a researcher from the NHK Broadcasting Science Research Laboratories, Kinuta, Setagaya, Tokyo, Japan [2]. The concept was then finalized by Yann LeCun, a researcher from AT&T Bell Laboratories in Holmdel, New Jersey, USA. The CNN model with the name LeNet was successfully applied by LeCun in his research on number recognition and handwriting [1]. In 2012, Alex Krizhevsky with his CNN application won the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge 2012. This achievement became a moment to prove that the Deep Learning method, especially CNN. The CNN method has proven to be successful in outperforming other Machine Learning methods such as SVM in the case of object classification in images.

CNN in this study, is used to detect and recognize real dogs and cat, and fake dog and cat. The test data used consisted of 100 photos of fake cats and 100 photos of fake dogs using the ReLU, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu activation functions. The results of the research will be in the form of mathematical analysis so that it is expected to provide an overview in implementing the ReLU, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu activation functions.

This paper is organized as follows: section I introduces the background, section II discusses about literature review from previous researchers, section III discusses about workflow or steps in study, section IV discusses about research results that are arranged in a logical order without bias or opinion, section V discusses about the results of the study findings that refer to the research objectives, and section VI is references that reinforce the author's argument.

II. RELATED WORKS

In neural networks, Convolutional neural network (ConvNets or CNNs) is one of the main categories to do images recognition, images classifications. Objects detections, recognition faces etc., are some of the areas where CNNs are widely used. CNN image classifications take an input image, process it and classify it under certain categories (Eg., Dog, Cat). Computers sees an input image as array of pixels and it depends on the image resolution. Based on the image resolution, it will see $h \times w \times d$ (h = Height, w = Width, d = Dimension). In Indonesia, study and implementation CNN are already quite a lot developed.

The first study is An Introduction to Convolutional Neural Networks (K. O'Shea et al., 2015). In this study, discusses basic concepts of Convolutional Neural Networks, explaining the layers required to build one and detailing how best to structure the network in most image analysis tasks [3].

The second study is ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional (A. Krizhevsky et al., 2016). In this study discusses deep convolutional neural network is capable of achieving record breaking results on a highly challenging dataset using purely supervised learning [1].

III. METHODOLOGY

To achieve the research objectives, need to do plan a sample selection, experiment, implementation, and testing. The related steps to achieve the methodology will be explained in points a to d:

a. Sample selection

The samples selected were dogs and cats. Where the dog sample amounted to 10.000 training data and 100 test data. While the cat sample amounted to 10.000 training data and 1.350 test data.

b. Experiment

The experiment was carried out by implementing CNN coding using the python programming language with the following steps in figure 1.

Fig. 1 Implementation CNN coding using the python programming

c. Implementation

Implementation using the Jupiter Notebook framework. The libraries used include the Conv2D tensorflow keras.

d. Testing

After the training data is implemented, the testing data in the form of images will be called to test the training results. The final result of testing is a prediction of the image according to the type of object in the image. The results of the testing output will be compared back with the actual results to measure how much accuracy the prediction feature is.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A. ReLU Activation Function

The process of running ReLU activation function in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running ReLU without data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 1, and running ReLU with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Result of Running ReLU Activation Function Without Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 1, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,4143
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,6896
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,5340
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,8140
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4173
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6661
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,5500
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,8060

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 39-51 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 2 Result of Running ReLU Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 2, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,5228
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,6912
3. The smallest training accuracy is:0,5309
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,7387
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4033
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6908

7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,5088
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,8188

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 68-85 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the ReLU activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using data augmentation is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

B. Sigmoid Activation Function

The process of running Sigmoid activation function in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running Sigmoid activation function without data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 3 and running Sigmoid activation function with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Result of Running Sigmoid Activation Function Without Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 3, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6932
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,7597
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4695
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5185
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6293
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,7375
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,3060
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,7080

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100 and the time required for the training process= 39-50 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 4 Result of Running Sigmoid Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 4, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6932
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,7531
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4734
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5125
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6439
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,7235
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,3137
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,7063

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100 and the time required

for the training process= 62-73 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the Sigmoid activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

C. Softmax Activation Function

The process of running Softmax activation function in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running Softmax activation function without data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 5 and running Softmax activation function with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5 Result of Running Softmax Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 5, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6931
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,6932
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4775
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5525
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6920
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6941
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,2980
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,6960

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 51-72 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 6 Result of Running Softmax Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 6, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6931
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,6932
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4913
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5153
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6926
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6954
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,3137
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,6850

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 79-108 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the Softmax activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this

is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

D. Softplus Activation Function

The process of running Softplus method in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running Softplus activation function without data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 7 and running Softplus activation function with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 Result of Running Softplus Activation Function Without Data augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 7, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6699
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,9093
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4915
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5970
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6312
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,7779
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,3140
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,6660

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 51-61 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 8 Result of Running Softplus Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 8, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,6908
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,8603
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,4900
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,5391
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,6618
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,7528
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,3038
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,6825

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 72-90 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the Softmax activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

E. Softsign Activation Function

The process of running Softsign activation function in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running Softsign activation function without data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 9 and running Softsign activation function with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 10.

Fig. 9 Result of Running Softsign Activation Function Without Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 9, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,4006
2. The biggest training loss is: 0, 6723
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,5835
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,8340
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4321
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,7662
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,4760
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,8060

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 42-56 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 10 Result of Running Softsign Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 10, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,5684
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,6864
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,5512
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,7069
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4518
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6806
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,5987
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,7862

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process = 64-117 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the Softsign activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

F. Selu Activation Function

The process of running Selu activation function in this research uses jupyter notebook software. The results of running Selu activation function without data

augmentation can be seen in Fig. 11 and running Selu activation function with data augmentation can be seen in Fig. 12.

Fig. 11 Result of Running Selu Activation Function Without Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 11, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,3564
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,8874
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,6430
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,8460
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4298
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6401
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,5980
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,7920

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 43-63 seconds for 1 epoch.

Fig. 12 Result of Running Selu Activation Function With Data Augmentation

Based on the results of running on the fig. 12, it is known that:

1. The smallest training loss of: 0,5801
2. The biggest training loss is: 0,8312
3. The smallest training accuracy is: 0,5312
4. The largest training accuracy is: 0,7016
5. The smallest validation loss of: 0,4570
6. The biggest validation loss is: 0,6160
7. The smallest validation accuracy of: 0,6700
8. The largest validation accuracy is: 0,7837

Where, to get these results, the number of epochs needed= 30, steps per epoch= 100, and the time required for the training process= 72-80 seconds for 1 epoch. Based on the results of running the Selu activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

V. CONCLUSION

In neural networks, Convolutional neural network (ConvNets or CNNs) is one of the main categories to do images recognition, images classifications. From this study can be discovered:

1. From each activation function that has been tested, it is known that the order of the best to the worst activation

function is ReLU, Softsign, Selu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus.

2. The best accuracy validation in the Relu activation function, which is 0.8188.
3. The worst accuracy validation in the Softplus activation function, which is 0.6825.
4. Based on the results of running the all activation function, it is known that the time required for the training process using augmentation data is longer, this is because the augmentation data is tasked with increasing the number of data points in the dataset before being used for machine training.

VI. REFERENCE

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